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Health physics and Radiation safety

Health physics is the science of radiation protection aimed at protecting people and the environment from potential radiation hazards while ensuring the harvest of beneficial uses of radiation. The science is devoted to radiation safety from the harmful effects as humanity continues to benefit from ionizing radiation in such areas as medical diagnosis and therapy and generation of electric power.

Photon and Electron Dosimetry

Personal dosimeters are used in measuring external radiation exposures. They record the absorbed radiation energy, dose, measured in grays (Gy) or the equivalent dose measured in sieverts (Sv). Personal dosimetry as the key part of radiation dosimetry is used to determine the doses absorbed by an individual exposed to radiation in relation to their work activities. There are two types of dosimeters, namely, passive dosimeters and active dosimeters. Common Passive Dosimeters are thermo luminescent Dosimeters (TLD) and the film badge. They produce radiation-induced signals stored in the device and then processes and the output analyzed. Active dosimeters are used to get real time value of exposure, such as the electronic personal dosimeters. They produce radiation-induced signals and display a direct reading in real time.

The gamma rays are ionizing radiation and are biologically hazardous as they are highly penetrative and can damage bone marrow and internal organs. The rays pass through the body easily and pose a huge challenge for radiation protection, which requires shielding from dense materials such as concrete and lead. Gamma ray detectors contain densely packed diamond. Some of the most used dosimeters are clear and dyed plastics such as colorless cellulose

triacetate and polyvinylchloride that show induced absorption bands in UV spectrum and in the visible spectrum for radiochromic dyed plastics, and blue cellophanes that show bleaching in the visible absorption spectrum (Das, 2017). High energy gamma energy is measured with survey Instruments and personal dosimeters including quartz-fiber electroscope and film dosimeters.

A dose response is based on the fact that radiation doses, greater than zero, in the lower dose range, increase the risk of excess cancer and contacting of heritable disease proportionately. Low doses of ionizing radiation induce beneficial health effects as they can stimulate the activation of repair mechanisms, thereby protecting against diseases not activated in ionizing radiation absence. Exposure to radiation just above the natural background level is not harmful but beneficial and higher radiation levels are hazardous.

Photon and electron emission have a number of important applications such as monitoring response of tumor to treatment and estimation of dose for targeted radionuclide therapy treatment planning. These radiations are highly stable and reproducible and this property is positively applied based on planar measurements with careful control of background activities during the acquisition of patient data and assessment of calibration factor.

Neutron Dosimetry

Neutron dosimetry is specific as neutrons are eclectically neutral particle and therefore subject to strong nuclear forces but not to electric forces. Neutrons do not directly ionize and are usually converted into charged particles to be detected (Andreo et al, 2017). Neutron detectors are equipped with converters to convert neutron radiation to common detectable radiation and one conventional radiation detectors such as the semiconductor detector, scintillation detector or gaseous detector.

Ideally, neutron and alpha radiations cause greater damage biologically for a certain deposition of energy per kilogram of tissue as compared to gamma radiation. The effects of any radiation increases with the transfer of linear energy (LET). The biological damage caused by neutron, proton and alpha particles is greater as they have higher Linear Energy Transfer than gamma rays which has low linear energy transfer. This is due to the fact that a living tissue is able to easily repair radiation induced damage spread over a larger area than that concentrated in a smaller area. One neutron or alpha grey causes more harm than one gamma radiation grey as the same physical dose causes more damage. Neutron radiation is able to induce radioactivity to bodily tissues and protection from it relies on radiation shielding.

Like in photon and electron emissions, dose response in neutron emissions is based on the fact that radiation doses, greater than zero, in the lower dose range, proportionately increase the risk of contracting cancer and heritable disease. However, even low doses of the radiation are harmful and can induce harmful health effects as they do not stimulate the activation of repair mechanisms, since they are more concentrated in one area as opposed to photon and electron which spread over a wide area. Exposure to any level of radiation including above the natural background level could be harmful and danger posed increases with increased level to hazardous exposure (Hine and Brownell, 2013). The presence of neutrons increases radiation-induced secondary cancer risk.

Estimating non-isotopic neutron dose is equivalent to quantities in neutron emission as multidirectional fields in a complicated undertaking which must be based on neutron fluence rate. The effectiveness of dose equivalent using weighted organ dose equivalent sum is not a quantity that is directly measurable. Computer modeling techniques and radiation field knowledge is used in its estimation. The determination of dose equivalent within a patient needs

the examination of neutrons as they are embedded in depth in tissue organs upon exposure and absorption.

Neutron emissions can also be applied in monitoring response of tumor to treatment and estimation of dose for targeted radionuclide therapy treatment planning. Neutron radiations are also highly stable and reproducible and this property is positively applied based on planar measurements. Non-radioactive sm-152 to sm-153 neutron activation is a valuable radio labeling method for oral dosage formulation behavior vivo study.

Works cited

Andreo, Pedro, et al. *Fundamentals of ionizing radiation dosimetry*. John Wiley & Sons, 2017.

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